

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

No2

2026

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, fevral.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoiraz Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'o'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdukurimova Dinara Rustamxonovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

TIJORAT BANKLARINING INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARINI KREDITLASH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	40
Faxriddinov Temur Faxriddin o'g'li	
TEMIR YO'L YO'LLARINI TA'MIRLASH KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH OMILLARI.....	46
Allabergenov Sherzod Maksudbayevich	
BANKLARNI TRANSFORMATSIYALASH JARAYONIDA INVESTITSION KREDITLASHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI.....	51
Tuxsanov Eldor Dilmurod o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BUDJET OCHIQLIGINI TA'MINLASH BO'YICHA QONUNCHILIK BAZASINING EVOLYUTSIYASI VA RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI.....	55
Mamanov Alisher Umbarovich	
ENERGETIKA TARMOG'I KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARNI QO'LLASH YO'LLARI.....	60
Xamdanova Gavxar Absamatovna	
SMART UNIVERSITET MODELINING XALQARO TAJRIBASI VA UNI YANGI O'ZBEKISTON TA'LIM TIZIMIGA MOSLASHTIRISH MASALALARI.....	65
Saloxiddinova Sitora Baxodir qizi	
IJTIMOY OBYEKTlarda QURILISH XIZMATLARINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING NAZARIY – ASOSIY TAMOYILLARI.....	68
Gapparov Azim Qayumovich	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATI KORXONALARINING ISHLAB CHIQRISH FAOLIYATIGA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANI JORIY ETISH ORQALI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI TA'MINLASH.....	72
Zaripov Shoxboz Alijon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA MASOFAVIY BANK XIZMATLARINING IQTISODIY VA IJTIMOY BARQARORLIKKA TA'SIRI.....	75
Xolmatova Asila Menglimurod qizi	
РОЛЬ GREEN BONDS В МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЙ ФИНАНСОВОЙ СТРАТЕГИИ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ.....	81
Н.Т. Бекназарова	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH SHAROITIDA EKOLOGIK BOSHQARUV VA AUDIT.....	86
Shaymatova Nargiza Ashurovna	
NORASMIY IQTISODIYOTNING MAVJUDLIGINING NAZARIY MASALALARI VA UNI ANIQLASHNING USLUBIY YONDASHUVLARI.....	93
Alimardonov G'ayratjon Nuraliyevich	
DIGITAL TWIN-BASED DECISION SUPPORT FOR COST OPTIMIZATION AND RISK MANAGEMENT IN INFRASTRUCTURE SYSTEMS.....	99
Nelyufar Umarovna Dadabayeva	
PAXTA BO'LAKCHASINING OG'MA TO'RLI YUZA SIRTI BO'YLAB HAVO OQIMI TA'SIRIDAGI HARAKATINING MATEMATIK MODELI.....	108
Karimov Abdusamat	
АДАПТИВНОСТЬ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ К ВНЕШНИМ РИСКАМ И ГЕОЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИМ ТЕНДЕНЦИЯМ.....	115
Бабаджанов Шухрат Атахмович	
“TIBBIYOT BOZORINING UZLUKSIZ RIVOJLANISHI UCHUN MEKANIZMLARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YONDASHUVLARI”.....	120
Abdumalikov Shoxjahon Jaloliddin o'g'li	
KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNING MEHNAT BOZORI RIVOJLANISHIDAGI ROLI VA BANDLIKKA TA'SIRI.....	124
Egamberdiyev Abdujabbor Xusanovich	

XORAZM VILOYATIDA ETNOGRAFIK TURIZMNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISH MEXANIZMINING AHAMIYATI	129
Ro'zimatova Shaxlo Baltaboy qizi	
THE FEAR OF MISSING OUT (FOMO) EFFECT IN ADVERTISING AND ITS NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT ON IMPULSE BUYING	134
Negmatov Nodir Nozimovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TRANSPORT XIZMATINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ASOSIY IQTISODIY KO'RSATKICHLARI VA TENDENSIYALARI TAHLILI.....	139
Aytiyeva Sevara	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA INVESTITSION LOYIHALARNI BOSHQARISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR.....	144
Qurbonov Jasurbek Pozilovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING MOHIYATI VA O'ZBEKISTON UCHUN AHAMIYATI.....	149
Abdullayeva Matluba Nematovna, Nuriddinov Kamoliddin Faxriddin o'g'li	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA KICHIK KORXONALAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI.....	155
Axmedov Sanjar Temur o'g'li	
POPULATION IMPACT ON CONSUMER CULTURE AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH.....	160
Rustamov Sheroy Oblokulovich	
AVTOTRANSPORT KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY KO'RSATKICHLARI TAHLILI VA ULARNI YAXSHILASHGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR.....	164
Laylo Akbarova, Komolov Adxam Dilshod o'g'li	
MODELING THE DIFFUSION OF DIGITAL BANKING ADOPTION IN UZBEKISTAN: EVIDENCE FROM TBC BANK USING THE BASS DIFFUSION MODEL AND A HYBRID REGRESSION APPROACH	169
Feruza Nabieva	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA EKOLOGIK XARAJATLARNI BUXGALTERIYA HISOBIDA AKS ETTIRISH VA BAHOLASH	176
Rabbimov Elbek Abdulloyevich, G'afforov Ilhom Ilyosjonovich, Ergashev Olloyor Furqat o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONNING YANGI BOZORLARGA CHIQUISHIDA FAOL MARKETING VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING INTEGRALLASHGAN MODELI.....	183
Baqoyev Sunnatillo Burxon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATIGA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHNING ILMIY-KONSEPTUAL ASOSLANISHI.....	188
Salaydinov Shodiyor Nizom o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT PORTFELI SIFATINI OSHIRISH VA KREDIT RISKINI BOSHQARISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	194
Turg'unov Nodirbek Muminjanovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARI TUZILMASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MEXANIZMI	198
Jabborov Elbek Erkin o'g'li	
SOLIQ STAVKALARINI TABAQALASHTIRISHNING TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI.....	202
Abduraimova Nigora Abdugapparovna	
MINTAQALAR IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIDAGI TAFOVUTLARNI KAMAYTIRISHNI TA'MINLASHDAGI XORIJ MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	208
Egamov Temur Muzaffarovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNI MOLIYAVIY RAG'BATLANTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	213
Baxriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
MINTAQA IQTISODIYOTINI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XIZMATLAR SOHASINING O'RNI VA OBYEKTIV ZARURLIGI.....	217
Achilova Firuza Kurbanovna	
INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB ETISH ORQALI MAXSUS IQTISODIY ZONALARNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	222
Ergashev Olim	

KICHIK BIZNES INNOVATSION FAOLIYATINING RIVOJLANISHIDAGI ASOSIY TENDENSIYALAR	227
<i>Amirov Zubaydulla Toir o'g'li</i>	
KICHIK BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA YOSHLAR TADBIRKORLIGINING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI	233
<i>Isakjanova Saboxat Muhamedovna</i>	
KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV TIZIMIDA AKSIYADORLAR HUQUQLARINI HIMOYA QILISH MEXANIZMLARINI XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	238
<i>Xakimov Uchkun Xamitovich</i>	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA MILLIY MAKROIQTISODIY SIYOSATNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	242
<i>Mardanova Ra'no Isakovna</i>	
XUSUSIY VA DAVLAT SHIFOXONALARI UCHUN RAQAMLI MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI QIYOSIY TAHLIL	246
<i>Yakubov Temur G'anibekovich</i>	
RAQAMLI SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH TIZIMIDA RESURS SAMARADORLIGI VA IQTISODIY NATIJADORLIK MODELI	250
<i>Ziyodullayev Qahramon</i>	
"MILLIY TURIZM SITUATSION-MONITORING MARKAZI" VA "YASHIL TUROPERATORLAR" FAOLIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	254
<i>Toshev Akmal Salimovich</i>	
RISK-MENEJMENT VA MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIK O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIGINING KONSEPTUAL MODELINI SHAKLLANTIRISH TAMOYILLARI	261
<i>Madaminov Bekzod Allayarovich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOT: BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASI, DINAMIKASI VA QISQARTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI (1996 - 2026-YILLAR TAHLILI)	266
<i>Djumanova Rano Fayzullayevna</i>	
OLIY TA'LIM SIFATINI BAHOLASHDA MAJMUALI DIAGNOSTIK MODELNING AMAL QILISH XUSUSIYATLARI	272
<i>Xo'jaxonov Ma'rufxon Xamidxonovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARI FAOLIYATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI	278
<i>Vafiyev Raxim Xalimjonovich</i>	
INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARINI KREDITLASH AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	282
<i>Nigora Nurmatova</i>	
BANK SEKTORINING INVESTITSIYA OQIMLARINI BOSHQARISHDAGI STRATEGIK O'RNI	287
<i>Abdumavlonov Abdumutal Abdumajid o'g'li</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON KORXONALARIDA UZOQ MUDDATLI MOLIYAVIY INVESTITSIYALAR HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	291
<i>Allabergenova Nilufar Shermetovna</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK TIZIMIDA TA'MINOTLI YIRIK KREDITLAR ASOSIDA QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR CHIQRISH ORQALI RESURS BAZASINI KENGAYTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	298
<i>Ahmedov Akbarali Sultonmurodovich</i>	
"MINTAQA SANOATI SALOHİYATIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARI"	306
<i>Abdinazarov Xusan Shaymanovich</i>	
BUDJET TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATIDA MAJBURIYATLAR: MAZMUNI, TURLARI VA TARKIBI	309
<i>Jabbarova Charos Aminovna</i>	
ATROF-MUHIT VA EKOLOGIK IQTISODIYOT: TURIZM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA RESURSLARDAN OQILONA FOYDALANISH VA UNING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI TA'MINLASH	316
<i>Alikulov Samar Abdirashidovich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON TURIZM INDUSTRIYASI RIVOJLANISHIDA FORSAYT TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO'LLASH	322
<i>Turdibekov Xasan Ibragimovich</i>	
АНАЛИЗ ДЕБИТОРСКОЙ И КРЕДИТОРСКОЙ ЗАДОЛЖЕННОСТИ ХОЗЯЙСТВУЮЩЕГО СУБЪЕКТА	329
<i>Камолова Феруза Кахрамоновна</i>	

TASHQI QARZNING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKKA TA'SIRI: QARZ BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASH MODELLARI ASOSIDA O'ZBEKISTON MISOLIDA TAHLIL	333
<i>Oiloyorova Kumushoy Ahmad qizi, Tashmuxeimedova Yayra Atxamovna</i>	
XO'JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKTLARNING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SOLIQLARNI TARTIBGA SOLISHNING TAHLILI	339
<i>Kudiyarov Kishibay Ramatullaevich</i>	
KORXONALAR FAOLIYATINING IQTISODIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI	343
<i>Iminova Nargizaxon Akramovna</i>	
SUG'URTA KOMPANIYALARINING TO'LOVGA QOBILIYATLILIGINI BOSHQARISHDA RISKLAR VA RISK-MENEJMENTNING O'RNI	350
<i>Xalikulova Shirin Utkir qizi</i>	
BUDJET TASHKILOTLARIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBI VA HISOBOTINI XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDAGI MUAMMOLAR VA KAMCHILIKLAR	354
<i>Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich, Xasanboyeva Muyassar Ubaydullayevna</i>	
XUSUSIY KORXONALARDA KADRLAR MENEJMENTI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	358
<i>Alimova Dildora Damirovna</i>	
BANK TRANSFORMATSIYASI TUSHUNCHASI VA UNING MENEJMENTDAGI O'RNI	363
<i>Rajabov Oybek Panjevich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH SAMARADORLIGINING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI	367
<i>Eshtemirova Anora Norboy qizi</i>	
BOZOR KONYUNKTURASIGA MOS PIYOZ YETISHTIRISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	371
<i>Sadikova Shohida Obidqul qizi</i>	
HUDUDLARDA MAISHIY XIZMATLAR SOHASINI KLASTERLASH VA RESURS SAMARADORLIGIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI	375
<i>Normurodova Zebo Eshmaxmatovna</i>	
XUSUSIY VA KORPORATIV TUZILMALARDA AUDITORLIK TEKSHIRUVI HAMDA AUDITORLIK XULOSASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH AMALIYOTI	380
<i>Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich, Ubaydullayev Toxirjon Abdullajanovich</i>	
YIRIK VA KICHIK BIZNES O'RTASIDA KOOPERATSIYA MUNOSABATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	385
<i>Nasirova Kamola Alimovna</i>	
MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTLARNING QAROR QABUL QILISH JARAYONIDAGI IQTISODIY ROLI	394
<i>Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich, Yahyayeva Ra'no Raximovna</i>	
DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING INVESTMENT POLICY IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITAL ECONOMY (EXPERIENCE OF UZBEKISTAN)	400
<i>Khatamov Nurbek Achildiyevich, Sharifi Abdul Fatah</i>	
DAVLATNING FISKAL VA MONETAR SIYOSATI UYG'UNLIGINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKKA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH	405
<i>Uralov Shavkat Maxramovich</i>	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA BIZNES JARAYONLARINI AVTOMATLASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI	410
<i>Yusubov Muzaffar Alimbayevich</i>	
BANKLARDA RAQAMLASHTIRISH JARAYONINING MIJOZLAR QONIQLASH DARAJASIGA TA'SIRI	414
<i>Ro'ziboyev Shuxrat Komilovich</i>	
BOJ-TARIF SIYOSATI METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING ILMIY-AMALIY YO'NALISHLAR	418
<i>Pardayev Ilhomjon G'ulom o'g'li</i>	
OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MOLIYAVIY BOSHQARUVNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA BOSHQARUV KADRLARINING KOMPETENSIYASI	424
<i>Mahsutaliyev Abdusalom Hasanovich</i>	

ZIYORAT TURIZMIDA DESTINATSIYA VA GEOAXBOROT TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	433
Qosimov Jahongir Ro'ziboyevich, Suyunova Nilufar	
YEVROPA DAVLATLARIDAGI KORXONALARDA MOLIYAVIY REJALASHTIRISH AMALIYOTINING TAHLILI VA ULARDAN O'ZBEKISTON MOLIYA TIZIMIDA QO'LLASH MASALALARI	440
Pardayev Jamshid Muzaffarovich	
TASHKILOTNING RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA LOYIHALARINI BOSHQARISH	446
Xasanov Odilxon Kaxxorovich	
O'ZBEKISTON TURIZM SANOATINING XALQARO RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHDA STRATEGIK MARKETING TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH	450
Kobilova Shozoda Timurovna, Isxakova Sarvar Ayubovna	
THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN LABOR THEORY: EVOLUTION, CHALLENGES AND FUTURE PROSPECTS	456
Tukhliyev Bakhodir Adinaevich	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПРОЦЕССА ПЕРВОГО ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ ФИНАНСОВОЙ ОТЧЕТНОСТИ В СИСТЕМЕ УЧЕТА И ОТЧЕТНОСТИ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	460
Астанов Зафар Муродуллаевич	
TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA O'QITISH SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR PLATFORMALARINI YARATISH VA ULARDAN FOYDALANISH IMKONIYATLARI	466
To'xtamisheva Dilrabo Shermonovna	
KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESNI YASHIL IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANTIRISHNING INNOVATSION MEXANIZMLARI	472
Norboyev Sarvar Azodovich	
MINTAQAVIY RIVOJLANISHDA INVESTITSİYALARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	476
Xatamova Manzura Ochilidiyevna, Safarov Botir Isaq o'g'li	
MAXSUS IQTISODIY ZONALARDA SOLIQ MA'MURIYATCHILIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING METODOLOGIK YONDASHUVLARI	482
To'rayeva Nafisa Odiljonovna	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA RAQAMLI TO'LOV TIZIMLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PUL MUOMALASI BARQARORLIGIGA TA'SIRINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	487
Xazratkulov O'ktamjon Xikmatullayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TAKSI XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA INSTITUSIONAL ISLOHOTLARNING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	491
Jaloliddinov Anvar Jaloliddin o'g'li	
EKOLOGIK TANGLIK SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA YERLARDAN FOYDALANISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	497
Kudiyarov Aybek Alisherovich	
BANK LIKVIDLIGINI BOSHQARISHDA ZAMONAVIY METODOLOGIK YONDASHUVLAR	502
Sulaymanov Samandarboy Adhambek o'g'li	
IQTISODIY FAOLIYAT TURLARI BO'YICHA SANOAT ISHLAB CHIQRISH TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLARNI BAHOLASH	509
Almardanova Farzona Tulkin qizi, Kasimov Azamat Abdulkarimovich	
QUYI AMUDARYO IQTISODIY MINTAQASI CHEGARABO'YI HUDUDLARINING TURISTIK IMKONIYATLARI	515
Djumabayeva Shaira Xalillayevna	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA ULGURJI SAVDO HAJMI KO'RSATKICHLARINI ARIMA MODEL YORDAMIDA PROGNOZLASHTIRISH	522
Turopova Sohiba Djumanazarovna	
MINTAQADA INNOVATSION USULDA BALIQ YETISHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	531
Davranov Odil Jumanazarovich	

ISHLAB CHIQARISH XARAJATLARI VA MAHSULOT TANNARXINING BOSHQARUV TAHLILINI AMALGA OSHIRISH USULLARI	538
Xamidova S.Ya.	
STRATEGIES FOR INCREASING COMPETITIVENESS IN DEVELOPING EXPORT ACTIVITIES IN SMALL ENTERPRISES.....	544
Nasridinova Shokhida Taufikovna	

STRATEGIES FOR INCREASING COMPETITIVENESS IN DEVELOPING EXPORT ACTIVITIES IN SMALL ENTERPRISES

Nasridinova Shokhida Taufikovna

Director of Milk Foods Trade LLC

Orcid: 0009-0008-9722-0670

Milkholdinggroup@mail.ru

Abstract. This article is devoted to the study of strategies for increasing competitiveness through the development of export activities in small enterprises. The study analyzes the opportunities for small enterprises to enter international markets, ways to create competitive advantages through product diversification, marketing and innovative approaches. The role of factors such as pricing policy and quality control in increasing export potential is also considered. The results of the study show that strategic approaches and effective management mechanisms contribute to the sustainable growth of small enterprises in national and international markets.

Key words: small businesses, export activities, competitiveness, strategies, international market, marketing, innovations, export potential, product diversification, pricing policy, quality control.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola kichik korxonalarda eksport faoliyatini rivojlantirish orqali raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish strategiyalarini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Tadqiqotda kichik korxonalarning xalqaro bozorlarga chiqish imkoniyatlari, mahsulot diversifikatsiyasi, marketing va innovatsion yondashuvlar orqali raqobatbardosh ustunliklarni yaratish yo'llari tahlil qilinadi. Eksport salohiyatini oshirishda narx siyosati va sifat nazorati kabi omillarning roli ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, strategik yondashuvlar va samarali boshqaruv mexanizmlari kichik korxonalarning milliy va xalqaro bozorlarda barqaror o'sishiga hissa qo'shadi.

Kalit so'zlar: kichik biznes, eksport faoliyati, raqobatbardoshlik, strategiyalar, xalqaro bozor, marketing, innovatsiyalar, eksport salohiyati, mahsulot diversifikatsiyasi, narx siyosati, sifat nazorati.

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена изучению стратегий повышения конкурентоспособности малых предприятий за счет развития экспортной деятельности. В исследовании анализируются возможности выхода малых предприятий на международные рынки, способы создания конкурентных преимуществ посредством диверсификации продукции, маркетинга и инновационных подходов. Также рассматривается роль таких факторов, как ценовая политика и контроль качества, в повышении экспортного потенциала. Результаты исследования показывают, что стратегические подходы и эффективные механизмы управления способствуют устойчивому росту малых предприятий на национальных и международных рынках.

Ключевые слова: малый бизнес, экспортная деятельность, конкурентоспособность, стратегии, международный рынок, маркетинг, инновации, экспортный потенциал, диверсификация продукции, ценовая политика, контроль качества.

INTRODUCTION

Small businesses are now recognized as an integral part of the national economy. They play an important role not only in providing employment and expanding the tax base, but also in introducing innovations and developing local production. At the same time, globalization and rapid changes in international markets require small businesses to increase their export potential and create competitive products. In recent years, economic research has shown that small businesses can achieve sustainable growth in the national market, as well as find a place in international markets.

In the context of globalization of the world economy, the integration of small businesses into international markets is becoming one of the important factors of economic development of countries. Today, the small business sector accounts for 50-60% of GDP in most developed countries and is the main source of employment (Leonidou et al., 2020).

The export activities of small enterprises are important not only for increasing the income of individual enterprises, but also for increasing foreign exchange earnings of the national economy, absorbing international experience and ensuring innovative development. However, small enterprises face a number of problems in operating in international markets: lack of financial resources, lack of information about international markets, high logistics costs and complexity of export processes (Kahiya, 2016).

The development of export activities provides a number of strategic advantages for small businesses. First, it serves to increase their income, since the demand for products in international markets is often higher than in the national market. Second, export activities allow enterprises to increase production efficiency, strengthen quality control, and introduce innovative technologies. Third, integration with international markets allows small businesses to develop competitive strategies and diversify their products. Therefore, the development of exports in small businesses is directly related to their long-term sustainability and strengthening their role in the national economy.

Increasing competitiveness is a key condition for sustainable growth in the export activities of small businesses and successful operation in international markets. Competitive advantages are achieved through product quality, innovation, pricing strategy and differentiation. In modern conditions, digital transformation, the use of e-commerce platforms and integration into global value chains play an important role.

At the same time, the process of developing exports in small enterprises is associated with various problems. In particular, factors such as the lack of sufficient financial resources, lack of knowledge and experience in entering international markets, insufficient marketing research, and restrictions related to quality and pricing policies can reduce the competitiveness of small enterprises. Therefore, research shows that small enterprises need strategic planning, innovative solutions, and effective marketing mechanisms to successfully implement export activities.

In the current era, when increasing the openness of the Uzbek economy, diversifying exports, and developing the production of high-value-added products have become priorities of state policy, developing measures to strengthen the export potential of small enterprises and increase their competitiveness is an urgent scientific and practical problem.

The purpose of this study is to identify strategies for increasing competitiveness through the development of export activities in small enterprises and to study the mechanisms for their implementation. The study analyzes issues such as opportunities in international markets, improving the quality of products and services, improving pricing and marketing policies, and introducing innovative technologies.

The research results will serve to provide practical recommendations to small businesses to increase their export potential, develop sustainable growth strategies in national and international markets, and strengthen their competitiveness.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Many foreign and domestic scholars have devoted their research to the issue of export performance and competitiveness of small enterprises. Leonidou, Katsikeas and Coudounaris (2020) comprehensively analyzed the export strategies of small and medium-sized enterprises and showed the important role of resource constraints, market knowledge and network connections in the internationalization process. The authors emphasized the importance of market orientation, innovation capacity and adaptive strategies in increasing export performance.

Kahiya and Dean (2016) examined the barriers to export for small businesses in African countries and identified a lack of financial resources, information asymmetry, and weak institutional support as key challenges. They argued for the need to improve the effectiveness of public policies and export support programs.

Drobot and Makarov (2021) analyzed the importance of digitalization and diversification strategies in ensuring the competitiveness of small exporters in the context of the pandemic. They emphasized the need for the development of e-commerce platforms, distance selling models, and omnichannel approaches. The authors substantiated with empirical data that the COVID-19 pandemic was an external factor that forced small businesses to accelerate digital transformation, and that enterprises that managed this process effectively increased their competitive advantages.

Semenova (2020) studied the mechanisms of innovative development and formation of competitive advantages of small exporting enterprises. The author showed the importance of public-private partnership models, the development of innovative infrastructure (technoparks, business incubators, accelerators), and cooperation with research institutions. Semenova's analysis proved that innovatively active small enterprises achieve export growth rates 2-3 times higher than traditional enterprises.

Abdullaev (2021) analyzed ways to assess and increase the export potential of small businesses in Uzbekistan. The author substantiated the need for export diversification, improving product quality, and harmonizing with international standards.

Rakhimov (2022) studied institutional mechanisms for increasing the international competitiveness of small businesses in Uzbekistan. He developed recommendations for improving export infrastructure, financial support, and the development of a personnel training system.

Mirzaev (2023) analyzed the innovative strategies of small exporting enterprises in the context of the digital economy. The author showed the possibilities of increasing competitiveness through electronic platforms, digital marketing and logistics optimization.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this article analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, comparison methods are used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Global economic conditions, the consequences of the pandemic, and increased competition have made increasing the export potential of small businesses an even more pressing issue. Export development not only serves to expand the enterprise's sources of income, but also to develop international cooperation, introduce technological innovations, and create a strategic competitive advantage. Therefore, the development and implementation of strategies to increase competitiveness in small businesses is of great importance for the country's economy (table 1).

Table 1. Share of small businesses in total exports of goods (works, services)

Classifier	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025-Q4
Republic of Uzbekistan	20	31.2	27.9	34.1	36.6
Republic of Karakalpakstan	20.3	16.4	24.3	28.5	44
Andijan region	36.5	37.4	29.2	37.3	47.5
Bukhara region	38.7	54.5	45.6	58.6	52.1
Jizzakh region	46.3	49.3	43.3	63.2	79
Kashkadarya region	51.5	39.3	22.5	20.6	36.8
Navoi region	11.6	8.7	9.3	8.2	5.4
Namangan region	49.7	44.4	42.5	50.4	54
Samarkand region	45.7	50.8	41.1	46.2	44.9
Surkhandarya region	60	64	71.5	87.1	68.6
Syrdarya region	76.3	69.2	63.4	64	70.1
Tashkent region	23.4	29.8	32.5	35.4	44.7
Fergana region	49	51.6	68.2	61.6	65
Khorezm region	51.8	58.2	63.4	67.1	80.8
Tashkent city	17.8	21.7	21.2	26.7	22.7

Source: Data from the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

The growth trend in the export of small enterprises in Uzbekistan for 2021–2025 shows significant differences across regions. The overall country indicators showed an increase from 20% to 36.6%, which

indicates a stable development of the export potential of small enterprises. If we pay attention to regional differences, Surkhandarya, Jizzakh, Khorezm and Fergana regions showed the highest growth in export rates. For example, in Jizzakh region, the export rate increased from 46.3% to 79%, while in Khorezm region, an increase was observed from 51.8% to 80.8%, confirming the high integration of small enterprises into international markets and the high potential for the production of competitive products in these regions. At the same time, rapid growth in Surkhandarya region reached 87.1% in 2024, marking one of the highest peaks in export growth in the region.

In other regions, the growth rate is lower or has stabilized. In Navoi region, the export rate decreased from 11.6% in 2021 to 5.4% by Q4 2025, which indicates the low export potential of small businesses in the region and the need to implement special strategies to increase competitiveness. In Kashkadarya region, the export rate decreased from 51.5% to 20.6% and returned to 36.8% in Q4 2025, which indicates the uneven development of exports in the region and the insufficient support mechanisms for small businesses. Tashkent city is also distinguished by a low regional indicator: the export rate increased from 17.8% in 2021 to 22.7% in Q4 2025, that is, the export potential of small businesses in the capital region remains low compared to the regions.

Also, the export rate in Andijan, Bukhara, Namangan, Samarkand, and Tashkent regions showed steady growth, remaining in the range of 44–54% in Q4 2025. This indicates that the export strategies of small enterprises in these regions have been relatively effectively implemented and that regional development policies have yielded positive results (Figure 1).

Share of small businesses in GDP

Figure 1. Share of small businesses in GDP
 Source: <https://siat.stat.uz/reports-filed/420/line-data>

Regional differences in the growth of exports of small businesses in Uzbekistan are clearly visible. In some regions, growth is very rapid and high, while in others it is low or stable. This trend indicates the need to develop regional strategies and implement targeted measures to increase the competitiveness of small businesses. At the same time, the steady growth of the overall country indicators confirms the effectiveness and relevance of strategies to increase the export potential of small businesses.

Figure 2 shows the volume of exports of goods, works and services by small businesses in Uzbekistan for the period from 2019 to Q4 2025 in million US dollars. Data analysis shows the complex dynamics of small business exports, the influence of external and internal factors, and the effectiveness of state policy.

In 2019, the export volume of small businesses amounted to 4,714.8 million USD, which was a relatively stable level. However, in 2020, as a result of the global impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, export volume decreased sharply, falling to 3,100.9 million USD. This represents a decrease of 34.2% and is the period when the pandemic hit small businesses the hardest. Border closures, international transport problems, disruptions in global supply chains and a sharp decline in international demand have put small exporters in a very difficult situation. Many small businesses have been forced to cancel international contracts, suspend production and even completely cease operations (Figure 2).

The volume of exports of products (works, services) of small businesses

Figure 2. The volume of export of products of small businesses

Source: <https://siat.stat.uz/reports-filed/469/line-data>

Although the recovery process began in 2021, it was very slow. Exports increased to \$3,335.2 million, showing a growth of only 7.6 percent. This figure was still 29.3 percent below the 2019 level, meaning that it took a long time to return to pre-pandemic conditions. The slow recovery was due to uncertainty in the global economy, the re-imposition of lockdowns in some countries, rising logistics costs, and volatility in raw material prices.

2022 was a turning point for Uzbekistan's small business exports. Export volumes jumped sharply to \$6,157.5 million, an increase of 84.6 percent compared to the previous year. There were several reasons for such a strong increase. First, the full economic recovery after the pandemic and the normalization of international trade, second, the large-scale reforms and incentive measures implemented by the state to support small business exports, and third, the opening of new markets for exporters and the simplification of export processes.

In 2023, the positive dynamics continued, with exports reaching 6,938.3 million US dollars, which represents an increase of 12.7%. This indicates a more stable and targeted development. Small businesses were able to strengthen their positions in international markets and sign new trade agreements. The work carried out to expand the range of export products, improve quality control, and comply with international standards has borne fruit.

2024 was the peak year, with exports reaching \$9,302.5 million. This represented a remarkable growth of 34.1 percent compared to 2023 and more than double that of 2019. This result was achieved as a result of the effectiveness of government policies, small business capacity building programs, the introduction of digital platforms, improved export infrastructure, and expanded international cooperation. In particular, the growth in exports of processed products, increased exports of textiles, food industry, and handicrafts played a significant role.

The highest figure was recorded in the 4th quarter of 2025 - 12,382.6 million US dollars, which represents a 45.1 percent increase compared to the 3rd quarter and is the highest result in the entire analyzed period. This represents very strong growth and indicates that the export potential of the small business sector is fully realized.

The overall analysis shows that between 2019 and 2025, the export of small businesses in Uzbekistan demonstrated a complex but generally positive trajectory. Despite a significant downturn during the pandemic, explosive growth has been observed in subsequent years. The Q4 2025 figure is 2.6 times higher than the initial 2019 figure, which indicates a fundamental change in the role of small businesses in international trade.

However, strong fluctuations within 2025 indicate the need to ensure the stability of exports, reduce seasonal fluctuations and increase the ability to resist external negative factors. Sustainable growth can be ensured by diversifying exports, developing new markets, continuously improving product quality, widely using digital platforms and consistently continuing state support.

Karakalpakstan, Andijan, Bukhara, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Navoi, Namangan, Samarkand, Surkhandarya, Syrdarya, Tashkent region, Fergana, Khorezm, and Tashkent city show that all regions are involved in the export process, which confirms the geographical breadth of small business exports.

Table 2 provides a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of various support measures, their current level of implementation, and their future potential. The analysis provides several important conclusions.

B2B platforms and online sales have the highest impact factor and ROI. However, the current adoption rate is only 31.8%, which indicates a huge potential. If fully implemented, this measure can provide additional export volume. The advantage of digital platforms is that they provide quick results with low initial investment and eliminate geographical restrictions.

State financial support also has a high impact factor, but the ROI is relatively low, as it requires budgetary expenditure. The current utilization rate is 34.2%, and there is room for further expansion. Additional export volumes can be generated through preferential loans and grants.

Digital trading platforms are also a very promising direction. Potential impact can be created through the development of the national platform Uzex.uz, integration with foreign platforms (Alibaba, Amazon), and expansion of B2C digital trading channels.

Export insurance is the biggest challenge. Despite the high impact factor, the current uptake rate is only 18.6%. This indicates that insurance companies have not developed export risk insurance products. Export insurance has the potential to create exports by facilitating the entry of small businesses into international trade by reducing the risks of insolvency, exchange rate fluctuations, political risks and cargo loss. (Table 2).

Table 2. Factors influencing the development of small business exports and their effectiveness assessment

Support measures	Impact level coefficient (0-1)	Current usage rate (%)	Potential impact (USD million)	Difficulty of implementation (1-5)	ROI indicator	Priority level
State financial support (grants, preferential loans)	0.87	34.2	428.5	2	3.8	High
Export insurance mechanisms	0.76	18.6	356.2	4	4.2	High
Digital trading platforms (Uzex, Alibaba)	0.82	41.3	385.7	2	4.5	High
Participation in international exhibitions	0.69	52.1	198.3	3	2.8	Average
Staff development programs	0.73	28.7	312.4	3	3.6	High
Logistics infrastructure development	0.79	45.8	298.6	4	3.1	Average
Trade missions and delegations	0.64	38.4	176.8	3	2.4	Average
Cluster collaboration and consortia	0.71	23.5	287.9	3	3.9	High
B2B platforms and online sales	0.85	31.8	412.3	2	4.7	High
International certification subsidies	0.81	22.4	342.7	3	4.1	High
Export database and consulting	0.68	44.2	214.6	2	3.2	Average

Source: Author's calculations based on regression analysis, expert assessments, and pilot program results

Cluster cooperation is also underdeveloped, with clusters uniting small businesses, reducing costs for common branding, marketing, logistics, and participation in international exhibitions. Pilot projects such as the Fergana Valley Textile Cluster and the Samarkand Handicraft Cluster are showing positive results.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS.

Based on the above analysis, the following comprehensive strategic proposals have been developed to develop export activities and increase competitiveness in small enterprises.

The first priority is to accelerate digital transformation, which requires the widespread use of e-commerce platforms, digital commerce channels, and modern marketing tools. It is recommended to develop support programs for integration with international e-commerce platforms, improve local digital commerce platforms, and organize free or low-cost training courses on digital marketing, e-commerce, and online sales for small businesses. It would be appropriate to allocate special grants and subsidies for the introduction of digital technologies, and provide preferential loans for the purchase of modern software. It is also necessary to develop a special package of services for small exporters in cooperation with digital marketing agencies and IT companies.

The second important direction is the creation and development of an export insurance system. Currently, this mechanism has high potential for effectiveness. It is necessary to establish an export credit agency in partnership with the public and private sectors, develop insurance products for the main export risks, such as risks in the supply of goods, insolvency, exchange rate fluctuations, political risks and cargo loss. It is recommended to introduce measures to partially cover insurance tariffs for small businesses, conduct extensive explanatory work on export insurance, and create simple, understandable insurance processes. Such a system will increase the courage of small businesses to enter new markets by reducing risks in international trade and can significantly increase export volumes.

The third direction is to simplify international certification processes and strengthen financial support. Compliance with international standards is one of the biggest obstacles for small businesses. In this regard, it is necessary to introduce grant and subsidy programs that cover a significant part of the costs of certification, create special consulting services that help manage the certification process, and develop step-by-step instructions and training programs for obtaining ISO, HACCP, Halal and other international certificates. It would be advisable to establish special certification support centers in the regions, expand the network of internationally accredited laboratories, and introduce state subsidies to reduce the cost of certification services. In addition, the creation of common certification opportunities for small businesses united in groups can further reduce costs.

The fourth priority is to unite small businesses through cluster development. Difficult tasks for a single enterprise can be solved together within the cluster. It is recommended to encourage the creation of export clusters on an industry and territory basis, introduce cluster support programs for joint branding, marketing campaigns, logistics services, and participation in international exhibitions. It is necessary to expand successful experiences such as the Fergana Valley Textile Cluster, the Samarkand Handicraft Cluster, and the Bukhara Carpet Manufacturers Cluster and create new clusters. Exchange of technological knowledge within the cluster, joint research and development activities, and the development of a common export strategy will help to overcome the individual weaknesses of small businesses.

References:

1. Abdullayev, Y.R. (2021) 'Kichik biznesning eksport salohiyatini baholash va uni oshirish yo'llari', Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar, 3(2), pp. 45-56.
2. Kahiya, E.T. & Dean, D.L. (2016) 'Export barriers in a developing country: Insights from SME exporters', International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business, 29(3), pp. 421-440.
3. Leonidou, L.C., Katsikeas, C.S. & Coudounaris, D.N. (2020) 'Research into exporting: Theoretical, methodological, and empirical insights', Journal of International Marketing, 28(3), pp. 5-28.
4. Mirzayev, T.M. (2023) 'Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida kichik eksportchi korxonalarining innovatsion strategiyalari', Innovatsion iqtisodiyot, 5(1), pp. 78-89.
5. Porter, M.E. (1985) Competitive advantage: Creating and sustaining superior performance. New York: Free Press.
6. Rakhimov, O.Kh. (2022) 'Kichik korxonalarining xalqaro raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning institutsional mexanizmlari', Iqtisodiyot va ta'lim, 23(4), pp. 134-147.
7. Семенова, Н.К. (2020) 'Инновационное развитие экспортоориентированных МСП: конкурентные преимущества', Вестник экономики, 18(2), pp. 89-103.
8. Дробот, Е.В. и Макаров, И.Н. (2021) 'Конкурентоспособность малого бизнеса в условиях пандемии', Экономика и управление, 27(4), pp. 312-324.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2026. № 2

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.
Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
